

DIGESTIBILITY OF CEREAL STARCHES BY TAKA-DIASTASE AND PANCREATIN AT DIFFERENT p_H AND AT $38.5^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$

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The digestibility of cereal starches (bavato, kodari, ghau, chokha, jowar, bajari, morivo and cheno) by Taka-diestase and pancreatin at different p_H and at $38.5^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ has been studied. The optimum p_H for digestibility for all starches has been found to be 6.5. Taka-diestase has better activity than pancreatin. The maximum digestibility of different starches is approximately the same.

Divergent views prevail regarding the digestibility of different grains. Thus, it is believed that in Gujarat green gram is more digestible than wheat (ghau) or rice (chokha), while in U.P., wheat is considered to be more digestible than either gram (chana) or rice. Similarly in U.S.A. and Europe, arrowroot crackers are regarded as the easily digestible products.

The diet of the people of Gujarat is almost entirely vegetarian, and hence, cereals and pulses form vital portion of their daily diet. Starch, which forms the main bulk of carbohydrate in food grains, provides about 50% of the daily requirements of the energy. So it was thought desirable to undertake a systematic study of the digestibility of starches of cereals from Gujarat.

Basu and Sarkar (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1935, 22, 745) studied the action of Taka-diestase on the starches from different varieties of rice, and observed that the different varieties differed in their digestibility. Starch from par-boiled rice is more rapidly digested than that obtained from sun-dried rice, presumably due to dextrinisation. Gorbach (*Fett. Seifen*, 1941, 48, 308) studied the action of β -amylase on the hydrolysis of bean starch and found the optimum p_H for hydrolysis between 4.8 and 5.0.

The digestibility is studied by two methods. In the biological methods it is carried out with animals by feeding them and studying changes in the metabolites. In the laboratory method, the hydrolysis of starch is studied by converting them into monosaccharides. Laboratory method is simple and the uniformity of condition can be maintained more accurately than with animal experiments.

In the present investigation the hydrolysis of starches of cereals by Taka-diestase and pancreatin has been studied at $38.5^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ at different p_H .

EXPERIMENTAL

Weighed amount of the starch sample (0.2 g.) was taken into a 100 c.c. conical flask and 20 c.c. of distilled water added to make a thin paste by keeping the flask in a boiling water-bath for 5 minutes till all the granules of starch had gelatinised. It was then cooled and 20 c.c. of a buffer solution of the required p_H was added, followed by 20 c.c. of the enzyme solution. The enzyme solution was prepared in such a concentration that when 10 c.c. of it was added, the strength of it in the bulk was 0.5%. The flask was kept at $38.5^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ for 30 minutes. The enzyme was destroyed by adding 25 c.c. of

Fehling-A solution, succeeded by equal volume of the Fehling-B. The flask was heated on a regulated electric heater. It started boiling within four minutes and boiling was continued for two minutes. The flask was kept covered with a watch-glass during heating. The solution was filtered hot at once through asbestos mat in a porcelain Gooch crucible under suction. The precipitates were washed with hot water till free from either copper sulphate or sodium hydroxide. The asbestos mat was transferred into a conical flask with the aid of a pointed glass rod and 50 c.c. of ferric alum solution was added through the Gooch crucible and the precipitate of cuprous oxide was completely dissolved by vigorous shaking. It was titrated against standard KMnO_4 solution, using *o*-phenanthroline as an indicator. The end-point was marked by the change of colour from brown to green. Copper was calculated from the KMnO_4 reading. Reducing sugar equivalent to weight of copper was obtained from Hammond's table. A blank determination was also carried out with the same volume of the enzyme and buffer solution as was used with the sample.

Weight of hydrolysable starch = dextrose $\times$ 0.93.

TABLE I

Hydrolysis of cereal starches by Taka-diastase at different p_H .

Period of hydrolysis = 30 minutes. Enzyme conc. = 0.5% Temp. = $38.5^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$.
(Expressed on the basis of total hydrolysable starch).

p_H .	Bavato.	Kodari.	Ghau.	Chokha.	Jowar.	Bajari.	Moriyo.	Cheno.
A. With Taka-diastase.								
3.05	31.62%	36.27%	45.57%	38.31%	37.20%	40.50%	37.66%	38.59%
3.72	47.42	48.91	47.89	38.40	40.10	44.10	42.98	43.98
4.35	52.63	53.19	55.05	55.80	46.00	55.00	48.54	46.96
5.00	58.12	54.87	55.33	51.60	51.70	58.69	49.90	51.70
5.80	55.98	53.19	54.59	46.03	50.22	55.98	51.70	50.22
6.50	58.86	54.30	55.98	55.60	52.17	59.08	54.03	53.13
7.02	50.44	50.77	52.35	57.19	46.96	54.10	49.56	51.52
7.65	49.25	45.57	41.85	51.47	41.10	48.60	46.03	44.4
B. With Pancreatin.								
3.05	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
3.72	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
4.35	22.32	35.52	38.59	35.34	23.25	28.39	37.20	26.97
5.00	37.20	39.06	40.99	38.59	41.38	46.50	43.24	36.73
5.80	36.72	31.15	39.52	38.13	38.13	45.10	39.90	32.08
6.50	39.06	33.01	41.65	39.06	39.06	45.57	40.92	35.80
7.02	33.06	30.87	37.20	34.87	38.59	40.90	39.99	33.48
7.65	33.94	28.83	32.73	34.13	29.76	39.06	38.59	30.96

DISCUSSION

Gorbach (*loc.cit.*) found the optimum p_H for the hydrolysis of beap starch between 4.8 and 5.0. The value rapidly falls on both sides. In the case of cereal starches we have found higher activity at p_H 5.0 and 6.5 with both the enzymes. It is also to be

noted that between these two enzymes there is no marked difference in digestibility, so far as their maximum activity on starch is concerned, though the course it is slightly different.

From Figs. 1 and 2 it can be seen that the hydrolysis is rapid at first and then it falls in the region of pH 5.5 to 5.8 and it rises up to 6.5, ultimately showing a uniform fall. This suggests that the breakdown of the starch molecules is very rapid on acidic side towards neutral point. It is also to be noted that pulse starches do not hydrolyse at pH below 4.0. The same is the behaviour of cereal starches. The percentage of hydrolysable starch is higher in the case of Taka-diaztase than that in the case of pancreatin at corresponding pH values, showing that it depends upon the type and activity of the enzyme.

According to Prošin (Zapiski Voronezh Selskoshoz Inst. 19 No. 1, 1941, 177-83; *Kim. Ref. Zhar*, 1941, 4, No. 6, 53) the velocity of saccharification of starch by diastase is related to the phosphorus content, but, so far as cereal starches are concerned, it has been found that such is not the case.

It is also observed that the grain size has some effect on the digestibility, and the results agree to the statement made by Basu *et al.* (*loc.cit.*) that the digestibility differs according to the fineness of the starch grain.

It is a common belief that the digestibility differs from starch to starch but from the experimental results it can be seen that it is practically the same for every starch.

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